

Review on Genus *Acacia*: Special Reference to *Vachelli aeburnea* – an Unexplored Traditional Medicinal Plant of Indian Subcontinent

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Abstract: *The medicinal plants are widely used by the traditional medical practitioners for curing various diseases in their day to day practice. Vachelliaeburnea (Mimosaceae) is one of traditional medicinal plant in India which is used for treatment of various diseases. Different parts of plants (i.e., leaves, bark, stem, and fruits even whole plant) have shown to have various pharmacological activities like antimicrobial activity, antioxidant activity, hepatoprotective activity, antimalarial activity, anti-diabetic activity, anti asthmatic and antibacterial Activity. Phytochemicals reported in the plants have been listed based on their pharmacological activity. Although Phytopharmacological reports are very less, still it is considered as a valuable source of treatment against various diseases*

Keywords: Vachellia eburnean, Antimalarial activity, Anti-diabetic activity, Asthmatic

I. INTRODUCTION

Acacia eburnea (L.f.) Willd., Sp. Pl. 4: 1081. 1806; Baker in Hook. f., Fl. Brit. .Small trees; young branches purplish-brown. Stipular spines straight, varying 3-6.5 cm long, gradually tapering from a broad base to a very sharp point, ivory white, polished. Leaves c. 2.5 cm long; pinnate up to 7 pairs, 1.5 cm long; sessile or nearly so; leaflets 5-8 pairs, upto0.4 cm long, linear, subobtus, pubescent on both sides. Flowers bright yellow with a disagreeable odor, in globose heads 9 mm in diameter; peduncles axillary, pubescent; bracts about the middle of the peduncle. Calyx 1.5 mm long, campanulate; teeth short, deltoid. Corolla 3 mm long, lobes ovate-oblong, acute. Ovary stalked, glabrous. Pods stalked 6-10 x 0.5-1 cm, flat, slightly curved, and indented on both sutures, longitudinally veined, glabrous. Seeds 6-10. Phenology: Flowering: November-February & Fruiting: March-May. Distribution: World: Afghanistan, Arabia, Pakistan, Sri Lanka and INDIA: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Gujarat, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra: Osmanabad, Solapur and Yavatmal. Ecological Note: Frequent in open scrub jungles, and bunds of field in Solapur region in state. Note: *Acacia eburnea* (L. f.) Willd., is very similar to *Acacia campbellii* Arn., but distinct by white thorns. Specimen Examined: Dharwad, 1889, W. A. Talbot 3969 (BSI, Pune); Ganesh Khind (Pune).

The bark of *A. eburnea* has been reported to possess antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties (Srivastava et al., 2011). It has been traditionally used for the treatment of fever, diarrhea, dysentery, and skin diseases. The bark extract has also been reported to have wound healing properties (Jain et al., 2016. Khan & Hafiz 2023).

The leaves of *A. eburnea* have been reported to have antioxidant, antidiabetic, and hepatoprotective properties (Kumar et al., 2011). They have been traditionally used for the treatment of diabetes, liver disorders, and as a general tonic. The leaves have also been reported to have antitumor properties (Jain et al., 2016).

The pods of *A. eburnea* have been reported to have hypoglycemic and antidiabetic properties (Yadav et al., 2011). They have been traditionally used for the treatment of diabetes and liver disorders. The pods have also been reported to have antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Jain et al., 2016, J, Jeba et al., 2022).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study site Maharashtra State is fundamentally a part of Miraj Tahasil, which covers a large area of *Acacia eburnea* species. Among these types dry tropical forests includes the „Babul (*Acacias*) forests“ which mainly came across 7 district of the Deccan (Desh) division in the state and most likely to be the „residence of *Acacias*“ in Maharashtra. More

importance was mainly given to dry tropical forests type of vegetation in the state. During the field visits, observations were made on distribution, phenology, Enzymatic activity, present status, reproductive behavior and habitat of the *Acacia* species (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2016).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The genus *Acacia* is known for its diverse range of medicinal properties, including anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-cancer, and antioxidant effects (Patil and Khan 2017a and 2017b Singh *et al.*, 2021). *Vachelliaeburnea* (Roxb.) P.J.H. Hurter & Mabb is a member of the *Acacia* genus that has not been extensively studied for its medicinal properties (Garg & Kumar, 2017). However, studies have shown that *Vachelliaeburnea* has potential therapeutic properties, such as anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antimicrobial activities (Singh *et al.*, 2021). In traditional medicine, *Vachelliaeburnea* is used for the treatment of various ailments, such as respiratory disorders, fever, wounds, and skin diseases (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2016).

Enzymatic and hormonal studies

Enzymatic and hormonal studies are an important aspect of plant biology and traditional medicine research. These studies help to identify the active compounds present in plants and their mechanisms of action (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2016). *Vachelliaeburnea* is a species of plant that has been used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various diseases. However, there is limited information on its enzymatic and hormonal properties (Taiz *et al.*, 2010, Singh *et al.*, 2021).

To conduct a study on enzymatic and hormonal properties of *Vachelliaeburnea*, one would typically start by collecting samples of the plant from the wild or growing them under controlled conditions (Garg *et al.*, 2017). The samples are then subjected to various biochemical and molecular biology techniques to identify and quantify the enzymes and hormones present in the plant. Enzymatic assays can be used to measure the activity of specific enzymes, while hormonal assays can be used to measure the levels of various hormones (Kuo, Y. H. and Lin, Y. S. 2017).

The results of such a study can provide valuable information on the potential therapeutic benefits of *Vachelliaeburnea* and its active compounds (Saini *et al.*, 2019, Tanveer *et al.*, 2020). However, it is important to note that enzymatic and hormonal studies alone are not sufficient to establish the efficacy or safety of a traditional medicine. Clinical trials and other studies are necessary to validate the medicinal properties of a plant and its extracts (Jain *et al.*, 2014, Mithila, J. and Hall, J. C. 2017).

According to K.R.Gandhe(2007)*Acacia eburnea* producing hypertrophy of infected parts, mainly thorns, inflorescence, flower and fruits. The hypertrophied part is edible and consumed with relish and also studied enzymatic during disease developing fungi.

Molecular characterization:

Dhakad Kumar (2018) suggested that *A. pseudoeburnea* is genetically similar to *Acacia nilotica* based on DNA sequence of *rbcL* gene,

Cytological and Antimicrobial activity:

Dr.S B Divya (2023) revealed that *Acacia nilotica* & *Thymus vulgaris* based mouthwash is more antimicrobial and less cytotoxic than chlorhexidine mouthwash.

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